

Astrometric precision of GAIA (2)

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SAG_LL_017

1 Introduction

This note gives estimates of the astrometric precision of GAIA as a function of magnitude and colour. The estimation is based on the method described in the GAIA Payload Definition Document [1], using optical and detector characteristics essentially as specified by MMS in January 1998 [2] and updated in March/April [3]. The estimates contain realistic assumptions on all the degrading effects that are considered, plus an explicit error margin.

The present document is a revision of SAG_LL_015 (Astrometric precision of GAIA, 23 March 1998), taking into account updated parameters, comments received since the previous note, and error margins as discussed at SAG7. The detailed assumptions are given in Section 2. The main changes with respect to SAG_LL_015 are as follows:

- several modifications were made in the calculation of stellar fluxes (Section 2.1), resulting in a good overall agreement (to within ± 4 per cent) with independent flux calculations based on Kurucz ATLAS9;
- improved V , R and I passbands were taken from [7] (rather than [6]);
- the CCD area used for the precision estimation is increased from 0.210 deg^2 to 0.231 deg^2 (Section 2.5);
- the read-out noise was increased from 5 to 10 electrons RMS;
- the background is calculated for samples of 1×7 pixels rather than 1×4 pixels, although the light loss by cross-scan diffraction is kept at 10 per cent (Section 2.5);
- for faint stars, the standard errors are increased by $p_{\text{det}}^{-1/2}$, where the detection probability p_{det} is calculated as in Appendix B;
- a precision ‘floor’ of $\sim 4 \mu\text{as}$ for bright stars results from a combination of reduced integration time (to avoid pixel saturation) and metrology errors (Sections 2.5 and 2.8);
- an explicit error margin is included (a factor 1.2 on the astrometric standard errors);
- results are given not only as function of the V magnitude, but also versus I and the GAIA magnitude G defined in Appendix A.

2 Assumptions

2.1 Stellar fluxes

The relative energy distribution in various (real) stellar spectra were taken from a standard stellar spectrophotometric atlas [4]. For the present study 16 (dereddened) spectra were selected to cover most of the main sequence and a few giants (see Tables 3–8). The relative fluxes (in energy per frequency interval) were converted to absolute fluxes (in $\text{ph m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{nm}^{-1}$) for apparent magnitude $V = 0$ through multiplication by C/λ , where C is a constant determined for each spectrum by means of the conditions:

1. for an unreddened star of spectral type A0V and $V = 0$ the energy flux at $\lambda = 550 \text{ nm}$ should be $3.66 \times 10^{-11} \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$ ([5], Table 21), corresponding to $1.0133 \times 10^8 \text{ ph m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ nm}^{-1}$;
2. for other spectral types and for reddened stars, C is adjusted to give the same wavelength-integrated energy flux (not photon flux) as the unreddened A0V star, when weighted by the V band sensitivity curve in [7], Table 2.

Using the sensitivity curves in [7] for the (Cousins) R and I bands, the R and I magnitudes of the stars can also be obtained, using that $V - R = -0.01$ and $V - I = -0.02$ for the unreddened A0V star ([5], Table 27).

For application of interstellar extinction the curve in [5], Table 3, is used, with linear interpolation in $1/\lambda$.

2.2 Sky background

A value of $V = 21.0$ per arcsec^2 is assumed, and the colour is taken to be $V - I = 0.7$.

2.3 Mission parameters

The assumed spin rate is $120 \text{ arcsec s}^{-1}$. Revolving scanning is assumed with Sun/spin axis angle $\xi = 55^\circ$.

The mission length is $L = 5 \text{ yr}$, including a total dead time of 1 yr (20 per cent) for attitude and orbit manoeuvres and similar. Thus the total time available for observations is 4 yr.

2.4 Optics

Two telescopes are assumed, each with a rectangular pupil of $1.7 \times 0.7 \text{ m}^2$. In the software each telescope was represented by an interferometer with two rectangular pupils of width $D = 0.85 \text{ m}$ and baseline $B = 0.85 \text{ m}$. However, separate calculations were made to verify that the total flux and polychromatic optical PSF obtained with this software did indeed match those of a single rectangular pupil.

The focal length is 50 m and the optical transmittance 0.9 at all wavelengths.

Aberrations are assumed to give a Strehl ratio of 0.8 at $\lambda = 500 \text{ nm}$. This corresponds to an RMS wavefront error of $W = 37.6 \text{ nm}$. The aberrations are taken into account through scaling down the monochromatic PSF by the Strehl ratio as function of wavelength, $\exp[-(2\pi W/\lambda)^2]$, but without changing the form or width of the PSF.

2.5 CCD detectors

The quantum efficiency is taken from the curve for CCD#3 in the MMS report [2], here reproduced as Table 1. For the precision estimation only the CCD area of the ‘faint star astrometric field’ (without PSM) is considered [3]. This is taken to have an area equivalent to 122 chips of 2780×1920 pixels. The pixel size is $9 \mu\text{m}$ along scan and $30 \mu\text{m}$ normal to the scan. The total solid angle considered is therefore $122 \times 2780 \times 9 \times 10^{-6} \times 1920 \times 10^{-6} / 50^2 \text{ sr} = 7.033 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sr} = 0.231 \text{ deg}^2$ (per telescope). The integration time per chip (before readout) is 0.86 s .

For the calculation of the sky background it is assumed that 7 pixels in the transverse direction are added on-chip before readout (constituting one logical pixel or ‘sample’). The diffraction normal to the scan is not formally included in the basic estimation method. Nominally the 7 pixels should cover nearly all the light in the transverse PSF. However, to account for imperfect transverse centring, transverse motion of the image, and similar, it is assumed (conservatively) that only 90 per cent of the light falls within the sample. The readout noise is assumed to be 10 electrons RMS.

The electronic MTF is modelled by the exponential charge diffusion model proposed in [1], with lateral diffusion ($1/e$) length $d = 1.2 \mu\text{m}$. For $9 \mu\text{m}$ pixel width this corresponds to an electronic MTF of 0.85 at the Nyquist frequency, or $0.85 \times (2/\pi) \simeq 0.54$ in the total (electronic + sampling) MTF.

Stars brighter than $V \simeq 12$ will cause pixel saturation in the faint star astrometric field and will have to be observed with other CCDs permitting a shorter integration time. Effectively this means that the precision does not improve for brighter stars but remains at a roughly constant level up to $V \simeq 6$. This effect is included in the precision estimation by putting an upper limit of 5×10^5 electrons on the total charge within the PSF at readout. This limit is reached in 0.86 s for a star of magnitude $G = 11.9$ (Appendix A).

Table 1. Assumed quantum efficiency of CCD detectors (CCD#3). Linear interpolation is used between the tabulated values.

λ	Q_λ	λ	Q_λ	λ	Q_λ	λ	Q_λ
300	0.00	500	0.77	700	0.91	900	0.55
350	0.05	550	0.82	750	0.84	950	0.38
400	0.21	600	0.90	800	0.77	1000	0.20
450	0.60	650	0.91	850	0.66	1050	0.00

2.6 Distortion and attitude errors

The total TDI error resulting from differential distortion within a single CCD chip and from attitude errors is set to 0.3 pixel RMS (assumed to be Gaussian). This affects the error assessment only through a statistical degradation of the MTF (PSF smearing).

2.7 Image location process

In [1] an analytical approximation of the Cramér-Rao bound was used to estimate the precision of the image location process in the presence of photon and readout noise. This approximation contains an empirical constant k which was conservatively set to 0.5 in [1]. For the present assessment this constant was calibrated by means of dedicated Monte Carlo simulations.

For each of 12 different spectral type/magnitude combinations, the RMS location error was calculated from 60 000 experiments, in which the true location was uniformly distributed over a pixel. The location process used the readout values (n_j) from 5 pixels ($j = 1 \dots 5$), where the middle one contained the actual centre of the PSF. The location was found by maximising the log-likelihood function

$$c(x) = \sum_{j=1}^5 [n_j \ln S_j(x) - S_j(x)] \quad (1)$$

where $S_j(x) = \beta + \alpha P(j - x)$ is the expectation of n_j if the PSF is centred on x (the along-scan coordinate of the image measured in pixels). α and β are the intensities of the star and background (assumed to be known). The function $c(x)$ was calculated in steps of 1/8 pixel and the maximum was found by first locating it to the nearest step of 1/8 pixel and then making a parabolic fit, using also the two adjacent steps, to refine the estimate.

Incidentally, it was found that this procedure gave no significant bias as function of sub-pixel position, and that the precision of the location was also practically independent of the position. Using 7 pixels instead of 5 would only give a very marginal improvement ($\simeq -1$ per cent in the standard error), while 3 pixels would deteriorate the results significantly (by +13 to 26 per cent). The location process failed (i.e., no maximum was found within ± 1 pixel of the expected centre) in only 12 of the 720 000 experiments; all of the failures occurred at $V = 21$.

Comparing the RMS errors found from these experiments with the analytical formula for different values of k , it was found that the analytical formula could reproduce the simulation results with k ranging from 0.32 (for $V \leq 15$) to 0.25 (for $V \sim 21$). For the following assessment the analytical approximation was used, assuming $k = 0.32$. For bright stars this gives practically the same results as the Monte Carlo simulations, while for faint stars it overestimates the standard error by some 4 per cent at $V = 20$ and up to 11 per cent for blue stars at $V = 21$.

2.8 Calibration, attitude and metrology

The location measurements in pixel coordinates need to be transformed to angular field coordinates through a geometrical calibration of the focal plane, and subsequently to coordinates on the sky through calibrations of the instrument attitude and basic angle. No complete model exists for this part of the accuracy analysis. It can be assumed that the errors are negligible for faint stars, where photon, readout and background (including crowding) noise will dominate. But for bright stars they could well be the limiting factor.

Lacking a better model, it is assumed that the contribution from attitude and field angle calibration errors is equivalent to the total weight of location measurements between $V = 12$ and 20 obtained in 0.86 s (one chip crossing) in a single field of view pointing to the Galactic pole. This gives then a constant contribution of $\simeq 25 \mu\text{as}$ (6 nm) to the standard error of the location process.

To this should be added metrology errors associated with the basic angle monitoring, and various systematic effects otherwise unaccounted for. We allocate about the same amount as above for each of these effects, making the total contribution equivalent to $\sigma_0 \simeq 40 \mu\text{as}$ (10 nm) at the level of individual chip crossings, or $\simeq 2 \mu\text{as}$ (1 nm) at the level of the final parallax error. Together with the bright-star limitation (Section 2.5) and error margin (Section 2.11) this results in an accuracy floor of about $4 \mu\text{as}$ for stars brighter than 12th magnitude.

2.9 Propagation to parallax and proper motion

The geometrical factor g_π relating the scanning geometry to the determination of parallaxes is set to

$$g_\pi = 1.64(\sin \xi)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

corresponding to $g_\pi = 2$ for $\xi = 55^\circ$. For proper motions the factor is

$$g_\mu = 6.0L^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where $L = 5.0$ is the mission length in years. g_μ is practically independent of ξ , if the mean precision in ecliptic longitude and latitude is considered.

2.10 Detection probability

A condition for observation in the faint star astrometric field is that the star was detected by the preceding sky mapper (PSM). For faint stars, this will only happen in a fraction p_{det} of the transits, where p_{det} is the detection probability. Consequently the astrometric standard errors must be multiplied by the factor $p_{\text{det}}^{-1/2}$, which is mainly a function of magnitude.

The calculation of p_{det} is a complex problem. For the present analysis a first-order calculation is made according to Appendix B. Results, given as function of the G magnitude, are shown in Table 2. (See Appendix A for the definition of G .)

Table 2. Detection probability as function of the G magnitude. α is the number of electrons produced by the star during 0.86 s, assuming 10 per cent transverse diffraction loss. The calculation of $p_{\text{det}}(G)$ is detailed in Appendix B.

G [mag]	19.0	19.5	20.0	20.5	21.0	21.5	22.0
α [e^-]	665	420	265	167	105	66	42
p_{det}	1.00	0.99	0.92	0.51	0.15	0.04	0.01

2.11 Error margin

An explicit error margin of 20 per cent is added on the astrometric standard errors resulting from the preceding analysis.

3 Results

Results for the estimated precision in parallax, as function of the V , I and G magnitudes, are given in Tables 3–5. Results for the precision in proper motion are given in Tables 6–8.

Acknowledgements

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References

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Table 3. Estimated precision in parallax (σ_π , in μas) as a function of spectral type (or colours), reddening (A_V) and V magnitude.

Sp	A_V	$V-R$	$V-I$	$V =$											
				10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
B1V	0.0	-0.12	-0.31	3.82	3.82	4.05	5.72	8.62	13.5	21.7	36.3	65.1	128.	291.	1700
A0V	0.0	0.01	0.01	3.87	3.87	4.07	5.76	8.68	13.6	21.9	36.6	65.4	129.	290.	1640
A3V	0.0	0.02	0.05	3.88	3.88	4.08	5.78	8.71	13.6	21.9	36.7	65.7	129.	291.	1650
A5V	0.0	0.08	0.17	3.90	3.90	4.05	5.73	8.64	13.5	21.7	36.3	64.8	127.	284.	1540
F2V	0.0	0.19	0.38	3.93	3.93	4.00	5.63	8.47	13.2	21.2	35.4	62.8	122.	269.	1330
F6V	0.0	0.25	0.53	3.95	3.95	3.95	5.55	8.32	13.0	20.8	34.6	61.2	119.	258.	1190
F8V	0.0	0.31	0.62	3.96	3.96	3.96	5.48	8.22	12.8	20.5	34.0	60.0	116.	251.	1090
G2V	0.0	0.34	0.72	3.98	3.98	3.98	5.43	8.12	12.6	20.2	33.5	58.9	113.	244.	1020
K3V	0.0	0.50	0.99	4.02	4.02	4.02	5.22	7.76	12.0	19.2	31.6	55.1	105.	221.	776.
M0V	0.0	0.84	1.72	4.10	4.10	4.10	4.54	6.60	10.1	15.9	25.8	43.8	79.8	161.	384.
M8V	0.0	1.24	3.23	4.27	4.27	4.27	4.27	4.39	6.32	9.63	15.1	24.4	41.0	73.7	146.
G8III	0.0	0.48	0.97	4.02	4.02	4.02	5.25	7.82	12.1	19.4	31.9	55.7	106.	225.	803.
K3III	0.0	0.64	1.19	4.05	4.05	4.05	5.01	7.41	11.5	18.2	29.9	51.6	96.8	202.	609.
M0III	0.0	0.80	1.72	4.12	4.12	4.12	4.56	6.62	10.1	16.0	25.9	43.9	80.1	162.	386.
M7III	0.0	1.98	4.69	4.39	4.39	4.39	4.39	4.39	4.39	5.13	7.61	11.8	18.7	30.6	52.7
B0IB	0.0	-0.11	-0.30	3.83	3.83	4.05	5.73	8.64	13.5	21.8	36.5	65.3	129.	292.	1710
B1V	5.0	0.76	1.68	4.12	4.12	4.12	4.58	6.65	10.2	16.1	26.1	44.2	80.7	163.	390.
A0V	5.0	0.89	1.98	4.17	4.17	4.17	4.27	6.11	9.28	14.6	23.5	39.3	70.3	138.	308.
A3V	5.0	0.90	2.02	4.17	4.17	4.17	4.24	6.06	9.18	14.4	23.2	38.8	69.3	136.	301.
A5V	5.0	0.96	2.13	4.18	4.18	4.18	4.18	5.86	8.86	13.9	22.3	37.1	65.7	128.	279.
F2V	5.0	1.06	2.33	4.20	4.20	4.20	4.20	5.53	8.29	12.9	20.7	34.2	59.8	115.	244.
F6V	5.0	1.13	2.47	4.21	4.21	4.21	4.21	5.33	7.94	12.3	19.7	32.4	56.3	107.	224.
F8V	5.0	1.18	2.56	4.22	4.22	4.22	4.22	5.17	7.67	11.9	18.9	31.0	53.6	101.	210.
G2V	5.0	1.22	2.65	4.23	4.23	4.23	4.23	5.04	7.46	11.5	18.3	30.0	51.6	96.2	199.
K3V	5.0	1.36	2.88	4.25	4.25	4.25	4.25	4.69	6.85	10.5	16.6	27.0	45.8	83.8	169.
M0V	5.0	1.69	3.55	4.29	4.29	4.29	4.29	4.29	5.44	8.13	12.6	20.2	33.3	58.0	110.
M8V	5.0	2.27	5.13	4.39	4.39	4.39	4.39	4.39	4.39	4.47	6.47	9.87	15.5	25.1	42.2
G8III	5.0	1.34	2.88	4.25	4.25	4.25	4.25	4.70	6.87	10.5	16.7	27.1	46.0	84.2	170.
K3III	5.0	1.49	3.07	4.27	4.27	4.27	4.27	4.41	6.36	9.69	15.2	24.6	41.4	74.4	147.
M0III	5.0	1.67	3.58	4.31	4.31	4.31	4.31	4.31	5.35	7.98	12.4	19.8	32.5	56.4	107.
M7III	5.0	3.08	6.56	4.47	4.47	4.47	4.47	4.47	4.47	4.47	4.47	4.92	7.25	11.2	17.7
B0IB	5.0	0.76	1.69	4.13	4.13	4.13	4.57	6.63	10.2	16.0	26.0	44.0	80.3	162.	386.

Table 4. Estimated precision in parallax (σ_π , in μas) as a function of spectral type (or colours), reddening (A_V) and I magnitude. Values exceeding 10000 μas are not shown.

Sp	A_V	$V-R$	$V-I$	$I =$											
				10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
B1V	0.0	-0.12	-0.31	3.82	3.82	3.82	5.10	7.57	11.7	18.7	30.9	54.0	103.	220.	875.
A0V	0.0	0.01	0.01	3.87	3.87	4.08	5.78	8.71	13.6	22.0	36.8	65.7	129.	292.	1670
A3V	0.0	0.02	0.05	3.88	3.88	4.14	5.89	8.90	13.9	22.5	37.7	67.7	134.	307.	1840
A5V	0.0	0.08	0.17	3.90	3.90	4.27	6.11	9.28	14.6	23.6	39.8	71.9	144.	339.	2230
F2V	0.0	0.19	0.38	3.93	3.93	4.51	6.54	10.0	15.8	25.7	43.6	80.0	162.	412.	3120
F6V	0.0	0.25	0.53	3.95	3.95	4.68	6.84	10.5	16.6	27.1	46.4	85.9	176.	480.	3910
F8V	0.0	0.31	0.62	3.96	3.96	4.79	7.02	10.8	17.1	28.0	48.0	89.3	184.	523.	4390
G2V	0.0	0.34	0.72	3.98	3.98	4.91	7.23	11.2	17.7	29.0	50.0	93.7	195.	587.	5090
K3V	0.0	0.50	0.99	4.02	4.02	5.19	7.71	12.0	19.1	31.4	54.6	104.	219.	754.	6860
M0V	0.0	0.84	1.72	4.10	4.14	5.89	8.90	13.9	22.4	37.4	66.6	130.	287.	1380	—
M8V	0.0	1.24	3.23	4.27	4.75	6.95	10.7	16.9	27.5	46.7	85.6	174.	417.	2820	—
G8III	0.0	0.48	0.97	4.02	4.02	5.20	7.72	12.0	19.1	31.5	54.7	104.	219.	757.	6880
K3III	0.0	0.64	1.19	4.05	4.05	5.38	8.04	12.5	20.0	33.0	57.8	111.	236.	885.	8200
M0III	0.0	0.80	1.72	4.12	4.16	5.91	8.94	14.0	22.5	37.6	66.9	131.	288.	1380	—
M7III	0.0	1.98	4.69	4.39	4.61	6.71	10.3	16.2	26.3	44.3	80.3	161.	366.	2050	—
B0IB	0.0	-0.11	-0.30	3.83	3.83	3.83	5.13	7.61	11.8	18.8	31.1	54.4	104.	222.	895.
B1V	5.0	0.76	1.68	4.12	4.13	5.86	8.86	13.9	22.3	37.2	66.0	129.	282.	1310	—
A0V	5.0	0.89	1.98	4.17	4.24	6.07	9.21	14.4	23.3	38.9	69.5	137.	303.	1500	—
A3V	5.0	0.90	2.02	4.17	4.27	6.11	9.27	14.5	23.4	39.3	70.2	138.	307.	1550	—
A5V	5.0	0.96	2.13	4.18	4.30	6.17	9.37	14.7	23.7	39.8	71.3	141.	314.	1620	—
F2V	5.0	1.06	2.33	4.20	4.37	6.28	9.56	15.0	24.3	40.8	73.3	145.	326.	1750	—
F6V	5.0	1.13	2.47	4.21	4.43	6.39	9.74	15.3	24.8	41.7	75.2	150.	339.	1900	—
F8V	5.0	1.18	2.56	4.22	4.43	6.40	9.76	15.4	24.8	41.8	75.3	150.	340.	1890	—
G2V	5.0	1.22	2.65	4.23	4.47	6.47	9.87	15.6	25.2	42.4	76.6	153.	349.	2010	—
K3V	5.0	1.36	2.88	4.25	4.51	6.53	9.98	15.7	25.5	43.0	77.7	155.	355.	2070	—
M0V	5.0	1.69	3.55	4.29	4.63	6.75	10.3	16.3	26.5	44.8	81.6	164.	381.	2340	—
M8V	5.0	2.27	5.13	4.39	4.67	6.82	10.5	16.5	26.8	45.4	82.5	166.	381.	2230	—
G8III	5.0	1.34	2.88	4.25	4.51	6.53	9.98	15.7	25.5	42.9	77.7	155.	355.	2050	—
K3III	5.0	1.49	3.07	4.27	4.51	6.54	9.99	15.7	25.5	43.0	77.7	155.	354.	2020	—
M0III	5.0	1.67	3.58	4.31	4.60	6.70	10.3	16.2	26.2	44.3	80.5	161.	372.	2200	—
M7III	5.0	3.08	6.56	4.47	4.47	6.07	9.20	14.4	23.2	38.6	68.4	133.	288.	1100	—
B0IB	5.0	0.76	1.69	4.13	4.14	5.88	8.88	13.9	22.3	37.3	66.2	129.	283.	1310	—

Table 5. Estimated precision in parallax (σ_π , in μas) as a function of spectral type (or colours), reddening (A_V) and G magnitude (Appendix A).

Sp	A_V	$V-R$	$V-I$	$G =$											
				10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
B1V	0.0	-0.12	-0.31	3.82	3.82	4.01	5.66	8.52	13.3	21.4	35.8	63.9	126.	283.	1600
A0V	0.0	0.01	0.01	3.87	3.87	4.07	5.76	8.69	13.6	21.9	36.6	65.4	129.	290.	1640
A3V	0.0	0.02	0.05	3.88	3.88	4.09	5.80	8.75	13.7	22.1	36.9	66.1	130.	294.	1680
A5V	0.0	0.08	0.17	3.90	3.90	4.10	5.82	8.78	13.7	22.1	37.1	66.3	131.	295.	1680
F2V	0.0	0.19	0.38	3.93	3.93	4.13	5.87	8.87	13.9	22.4	37.5	67.1	132.	299.	1690
F6V	0.0	0.25	0.53	3.95	3.95	4.16	5.92	8.95	14.0	22.6	37.9	67.9	134.	303.	1720
F8V	0.0	0.31	0.62	3.96	3.96	4.17	5.94	8.99	14.1	22.7	38.1	68.2	135.	304.	1720
G2V	0.0	0.34	0.72	3.98	3.98	4.20	5.99	9.07	14.2	22.9	38.5	69.0	136.	309.	1780
K3V	0.0	0.50	0.99	4.02	4.02	4.24	6.06	9.19	14.4	23.3	39.1	70.1	139.	315.	1810
M0V	0.0	0.84	1.72	4.10	4.10	4.34	6.25	9.50	14.9	24.1	40.6	73.1	145.	331.	1910
M8V	0.0	1.24	3.23	4.27	4.27	4.59	6.67	10.2	16.1	26.1	44.2	80.2	161.	372.	2250
G8III	0.0	0.48	0.97	4.02	4.02	4.25	6.08	9.23	14.5	23.4	39.3	70.6	140.	318.	1840
K3III	0.0	0.64	1.19	4.05	4.05	4.26	6.09	9.24	14.5	23.4	39.3	70.5	140.	316.	1780
M0III	0.0	0.80	1.72	4.12	4.12	4.36	6.27	9.54	15.0	24.2	40.8	73.4	146.	332.	1920
M7III	0.0	1.98	4.69	4.39	4.39	4.58	6.65	10.2	16.0	26.0	43.8	79.3	158.	359.	1950
B0IB	0.0	-0.11	-0.30	3.83	3.83	4.02	5.67	8.54	13.3	21.5	35.9	64.1	126.	284.	1610
B1V	5.0	0.76	1.68	4.12	4.12	4.34	6.24	9.49	14.9	24.1	40.5	72.9	145.	328.	1860
A0V	5.0	0.89	1.98	4.17	4.17	4.35	6.26	9.53	15.0	24.2	40.6	73.0	145.	326.	1790
A3V	5.0	0.90	2.02	4.17	4.17	4.36	6.28	9.56	15.0	24.3	40.8	73.3	145.	328.	1800
A5V	5.0	0.96	2.13	4.18	4.18	4.36	6.28	9.56	15.0	24.3	40.8	73.3	145.	328.	1790
F2V	5.0	1.06	2.33	4.20	4.20	4.37	6.30	9.58	15.1	24.3	40.9	73.5	146.	328.	1770
F6V	5.0	1.13	2.47	4.21	4.21	4.40	6.34	9.66	15.2	24.5	41.3	74.3	147.	333.	1820
F8V	5.0	1.18	2.56	4.22	4.22	4.38	6.32	9.62	15.1	24.4	41.0	73.8	146.	329.	1760
G2V	5.0	1.22	2.65	4.23	4.23	4.40	6.35	9.67	15.2	24.6	41.3	74.4	148.	333.	1810
K3V	5.0	1.36	2.88	4.25	4.25	4.40	6.34	9.66	15.2	24.6	41.3	74.2	147.	330.	1750
M0V	5.0	1.69	3.55	4.29	4.29	4.47	6.46	9.86	15.5	25.1	42.2	76.1	151.	342.	1840
M8V	5.0	2.27	5.13	4.39	4.39	4.77	6.99	10.7	17.0	27.6	46.9	85.7	173.	407.	2550
G8III	5.0	1.34	2.88	4.25	4.25	4.40	6.35	9.67	15.2	24.6	41.3	74.2	147.	330.	1750
K3III	5.0	1.49	3.07	4.27	4.27	4.38	6.31	9.60	15.1	24.4	40.9	73.4	145.	324.	1660
M0III	5.0	1.67	3.58	4.31	4.31	4.44	6.41	9.78	15.4	24.9	41.8	75.1	149.	334.	1730
M7III	5.0	3.08	6.56	4.47	4.47	5.04	7.46	11.5	18.3	29.9	51.1	94.6	194.	476.	3350
B0IB	5.0	0.76	1.69	4.13	4.13	4.34	6.25	9.50	14.9	24.1	40.5	72.9	145.	328.	1840

Table 6. Estimated precision in proper motion (σ_μ , in $\mu\text{as yr}^{-1}$) as a function of spectral type (or colours), reddening (A_V) and V magnitude.

Sp	A_V	$V-R$	$V-I$	$V =$											
				10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
B1V	0.0	-0.12	-0.31	2.29	2.29	2.43	3.43	5.17	8.08	13.0	21.8	39.0	76.9	174.	1020
A0V	0.0	0.01	0.01	2.32	2.32	2.44	3.45	5.20	8.14	13.1	21.9	39.2	77.1	174.	980.
A3V	0.0	0.02	0.05	2.33	2.33	2.44	3.46	5.22	8.17	13.2	22.0	39.4	77.5	175.	987.
A5V	0.0	0.08	0.17	2.34	2.34	2.43	3.44	5.18	8.10	13.0	21.8	38.8	76.2	170.	924.
F2V	0.0	0.19	0.38	2.36	2.36	2.40	3.38	5.08	7.92	12.7	21.2	37.6	73.4	161.	799.
F6V	0.0	0.25	0.53	2.37	2.37	2.37	3.33	4.99	7.78	12.5	20.7	36.7	71.1	155.	714.
F8V	0.0	0.31	0.62	2.38	2.38	2.38	3.29	4.92	7.67	12.3	20.4	35.9	69.4	150.	655.
G2V	0.0	0.34	0.72	2.38	2.38	2.38	3.25	4.87	7.58	12.1	20.1	35.3	68.0	146.	609.
K3V	0.0	0.50	0.99	2.41	2.41	2.41	3.13	4.65	7.21	11.5	19.0	33.0	62.7	133.	465.
M0V	0.0	0.84	1.72	2.46	2.46	2.46	2.72	3.95	6.05	9.54	15.5	26.2	47.8	96.4	230.
M8V	0.0	1.24	3.23	2.56	2.56	2.56	2.56	2.63	3.79	5.77	9.07	14.6	24.6	44.1	87.3
G8III	0.0	0.48	0.97	2.41	2.41	2.41	3.15	4.69	7.27	11.6	19.1	33.4	63.6	135.	481.
K3III	0.0	0.64	1.19	2.43	2.43	2.43	3.01	4.44	6.86	10.9	17.9	30.9	58.0	121.	365.
M0III	0.0	0.80	1.72	2.47	2.47	2.47	2.73	3.97	6.07	9.58	15.5	26.3	48.0	96.8	231.
M7III	0.0	1.98	4.69	2.63	2.63	2.63	2.63	2.63	2.63	3.08	4.56	7.06	11.2	18.4	31.6
B0IB	0.0	-0.11	-0.30	2.29	2.29	2.43	3.44	5.18	8.10	13.0	21.9	39.1	77.2	175.	1030
B1V	5.0	0.76	1.68	2.47	2.47	2.47	2.74	3.99	6.10	9.63	15.6	26.5	48.4	97.6	234.
A0V	5.0	0.89	1.98	2.50	2.50	2.50	2.56	3.66	5.56	8.73	14.1	23.6	42.1	83.0	185.
A3V	5.0	0.90	2.02	2.50	2.50	2.50	2.54	3.63	5.51	8.63	13.9	23.3	41.5	81.5	180.
A5V	5.0	0.96	2.13	2.51	2.51	2.51	2.51	3.52	5.31	8.31	13.3	22.2	39.4	76.7	167.
F2V	5.0	1.06	2.33	2.52	2.52	2.52	2.52	3.32	4.97	7.74	12.4	20.5	35.9	68.7	146.
F6V	5.0	1.13	2.47	2.52	2.52	2.52	2.52	3.19	4.76	7.39	11.8	19.4	33.7	63.9	135.
F8V	5.0	1.18	2.56	2.53	2.53	2.53	2.53	3.10	4.60	7.12	11.3	18.6	32.1	60.3	126.
G2V	5.0	1.22	2.65	2.53	2.53	2.53	2.53	3.02	4.47	6.91	11.0	18.0	30.9	57.6	119.
K3V	5.0	1.36	2.88	2.55	2.55	2.55	2.55	2.81	4.11	6.30	9.96	16.2	27.5	50.2	102.
M0V	5.0	1.69	3.55	2.57	2.57	2.57	2.57	2.57	3.26	4.88	7.58	12.1	20.0	34.8	66.0
M8V	5.0	2.27	5.13	2.63	2.63	2.63	2.63	2.63	2.63	2.68	3.88	5.92	9.31	15.1	25.3
G8III	5.0	1.34	2.88	2.55	2.55	2.55	2.55	2.82	4.12	6.32	9.99	16.2	27.6	50.5	102.
K3III	5.0	1.49	3.07	2.56	2.56	2.56	2.56	2.64	3.81	5.81	9.14	14.8	24.8	44.6	88.4
M0III	5.0	1.67	3.58	2.58	2.58	2.58	2.58	2.58	3.20	4.78	7.43	11.8	19.5	33.8	63.9
M7III	5.0	3.08	6.56	2.68	2.68	2.68	2.68	2.68	2.68	2.68	2.68	2.95	4.35	6.70	10.6
B0IB	5.0	0.76	1.69	2.48	2.48	2.48	2.74	3.98	6.08	9.60	15.6	26.4	48.1	97.0	231.

Table 7. Estimated precision in proper motion (σ_μ , in $\mu\text{as yr}^{-1}$) as a function of spectral type (or colours), reddening (A_V) and I magnitude. Values exceeding 10000 μas are not shown.

Sp	A_V	$V-R$	$V-I$	$I =$											
				10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
B1V	0.0	-0.12	-0.31	2.29	2.29	2.29	3.06	4.54	7.03	11.2	18.5	32.3	61.8	132.	524.
A0V	0.0	0.01	0.01	2.32	2.32	2.44	3.46	5.22	8.17	13.2	22.0	39.4	77.6	175.	999.
A3V	0.0	0.02	0.05	2.33	2.33	2.48	3.53	5.33	8.36	13.5	22.6	40.6	80.3	184.	1100
A5V	0.0	0.08	0.17	2.34	2.34	2.56	3.66	5.56	8.74	14.1	23.8	43.1	86.1	203.	1340
F2V	0.0	0.19	0.38	2.36	2.36	2.70	3.92	5.99	9.46	15.4	26.1	47.9	97.3	247.	1870
F6V	0.0	0.25	0.53	2.37	2.37	2.81	4.10	6.30	9.97	16.3	27.8	51.5	106.	288.	2340
F8V	0.0	0.31	0.62	2.38	2.38	2.87	4.21	6.47	10.3	16.8	28.8	53.5	110.	314.	2630
G2V	0.0	0.34	0.72	2.38	2.38	2.94	4.33	6.68	10.6	17.4	30.0	56.1	117.	352.	3050
K3V	0.0	0.50	0.99	2.41	2.41	3.11	4.62	7.17	11.4	18.8	32.8	62.1	131.	452.	4110
M0V	0.0	0.84	1.72	2.46	2.48	3.53	5.34	8.36	13.4	22.4	39.9	78.1	172.	826.	7890
M8V	0.0	1.24	3.23	2.56	2.85	4.16	6.40	10.1	16.5	28.0	51.3	104.	250.	1690	—
G8III	0.0	0.48	0.97	2.41	2.41	3.11	4.63	7.18	11.4	18.9	32.8	62.2	131.	454.	4130
K3III	0.0	0.64	1.19	2.43	2.43	3.23	4.82	7.49	12.0	19.8	34.6	66.3	141.	531.	4910
M0III	0.0	0.80	1.72	2.47	2.49	3.54	5.36	8.39	13.5	22.5	40.1	78.4	173.	828.	7900
M7III	0.0	1.98	4.69	2.63	2.76	4.02	6.16	9.71	15.7	26.6	48.1	96.3	219.	1230	—
B0IB	0.0	-0.11	-0.30	2.29	2.29	2.29	3.07	4.56	7.07	11.3	18.6	32.6	62.3	133.	537.
B1V	5.0	0.76	1.68	2.47	2.47	3.52	5.31	8.31	13.4	22.3	39.6	77.2	169.	785.	7480
A0V	5.0	0.89	1.98	2.50	2.54	3.64	5.52	8.65	13.9	23.3	41.7	81.9	182.	901.	8630
A3V	5.0	0.90	2.02	2.50	2.56	3.66	5.56	8.72	14.1	23.5	42.1	82.8	184.	928.	8900
A5V	5.0	0.96	2.13	2.51	2.58	3.70	5.62	8.82	14.2	23.9	42.7	84.3	188.	970.	9320
F2V	5.0	1.06	2.33	2.52	2.62	3.77	5.73	9.01	14.5	24.4	43.9	87.0	196.	1050	—
F6V	5.0	1.13	2.47	2.52	2.65	3.83	5.84	9.19	14.9	25.0	45.1	89.6	203.	1140	—
F8V	5.0	1.18	2.56	2.53	2.66	3.84	5.85	9.21	14.9	25.0	45.2	89.8	204.	1130	—
G2V	5.0	1.22	2.65	2.53	2.68	3.88	5.92	9.32	15.1	25.4	45.9	91.6	209.	1200	—
K3V	5.0	1.36	2.88	2.55	2.70	3.92	5.98	9.43	15.3	25.7	46.6	93.1	213.	1240	—
M0V	5.0	1.69	3.55	2.57	2.78	4.05	6.20	9.79	15.9	26.9	48.9	98.3	229.	1400	—
M8V	5.0	2.27	5.13	2.63	2.80	4.09	6.27	9.90	16.1	27.2	49.4	99.3	229.	1340	—
G8III	5.0	1.34	2.88	2.55	2.70	3.92	5.98	9.43	15.3	25.7	46.6	93.0	213.	1230	—
K3III	5.0	1.49	3.07	2.56	2.70	3.92	5.99	9.43	15.3	25.7	46.6	92.9	212.	1210	—
M0III	5.0	1.67	3.58	2.58	2.76	4.01	6.15	9.70	15.7	26.6	48.2	96.7	223.	1320	—
M7III	5.0	3.08	6.56	2.68	2.68	3.64	5.52	8.65	13.9	23.1	41.0	79.7	172.	659.	6140
B0IB	5.0	0.76	1.69	2.48	2.48	3.52	5.32	8.33	13.4	22.3	39.7	77.4	170.	786.	7480

Table 8. Estimated precision in proper motion (σ_μ , in $\mu\text{as yr}^{-1}$) as a function of spectral type (or colours), reddening (A_V) and G magnitude (Appendix A).

Sp	A_V	$V-R$	$V-I$	$G =$											
				10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
B1V	0.0	-0.12	-0.31	2.29	2.29	2.41	3.39	5.10	7.98	12.8	21.5	38.3	75.3	169.	958.
A0V	0.0	0.01	0.01	2.32	2.32	2.44	3.45	5.21	8.15	13.1	21.9	39.2	77.2	174.	983.
A3V	0.0	0.02	0.05	2.33	2.33	2.45	3.47	5.24	8.21	13.2	22.1	39.6	78.0	176.	1010
A5V	0.0	0.08	0.17	2.34	2.34	2.46	3.49	5.26	8.24	13.3	22.2	39.8	78.4	177.	1000
F2V	0.0	0.19	0.38	2.36	2.36	2.48	3.52	5.32	8.33	13.4	22.5	40.2	79.3	179.	1010
F6V	0.0	0.25	0.53	2.37	2.37	2.49	3.55	5.36	8.40	13.5	22.7	40.7	80.3	181.	1030
F8V	0.0	0.31	0.62	2.38	2.38	2.50	3.56	5.39	8.44	13.6	22.8	40.9	80.7	182.	1030
G2V	0.0	0.34	0.72	2.38	2.38	2.52	3.59	5.43	8.52	13.7	23.1	41.4	81.8	185.	1060
K3V	0.0	0.50	0.99	2.41	2.41	2.54	3.63	5.51	8.64	13.9	23.4	42.0	83.2	189.	1080
M0V	0.0	0.84	1.72	2.46	2.46	2.60	3.74	5.69	8.95	14.5	24.3	43.8	87.0	198.	1150
M8V	0.0	1.24	3.23	2.56	2.56	2.75	4.00	6.12	9.66	15.7	26.5	48.1	96.5	223.	1350
G8III	0.0	0.48	0.97	2.41	2.41	2.55	3.65	5.53	8.68	14.0	23.5	42.3	83.8	190.	1100
K3III	0.0	0.64	1.19	2.43	2.43	2.55	3.65	5.54	8.69	14.0	23.5	42.3	83.6	189.	1070
M0III	0.0	0.80	1.72	2.47	2.47	2.61	3.76	5.72	8.99	14.5	24.4	44.0	87.5	199.	1150
M7III	0.0	1.98	4.69	2.63	2.63	2.74	3.99	6.10	9.62	15.6	26.3	47.5	94.8	215.	1170
B0IB	0.0	-0.11	-0.30	2.29	2.29	2.41	3.40	5.12	8.00	12.9	21.5	38.4	75.6	170.	964.
B1V	5.0	0.76	1.68	2.47	2.47	2.60	3.74	5.69	8.94	14.4	24.3	43.7	86.7	197.	1110
A0V	5.0	0.89	1.98	2.50	2.50	2.61	3.75	5.71	8.98	14.5	24.4	43.8	86.8	196.	1070
A3V	5.0	0.90	2.02	2.50	2.50	2.62	3.76	5.73	9.00	14.5	24.4	44.0	87.1	197.	1080
A5V	5.0	0.96	2.13	2.51	2.51	2.62	3.77	5.73	9.01	14.5	24.4	43.9	87.1	196.	1070
F2V	5.0	1.06	2.33	2.52	2.52	2.62	3.77	5.74	9.03	14.6	24.5	44.1	87.3	197.	1060
F6V	5.0	1.13	2.47	2.52	2.52	2.64	3.80	5.79	9.10	14.7	24.7	44.5	88.4	199.	1090
F8V	5.0	1.18	2.56	2.53	2.53	2.63	3.79	5.77	9.07	14.6	24.6	44.2	87.6	197.	1050
G2V	5.0	1.22	2.65	2.53	2.53	2.64	3.81	5.80	9.12	14.7	24.8	44.6	88.5	200.	1080
K3V	5.0	1.36	2.88	2.55	2.55	2.64	3.80	5.79	9.11	14.7	24.7	44.5	88.1	198.	1050
M0V	5.0	1.69	3.55	2.57	2.57	2.68	3.87	5.91	9.30	15.0	25.3	45.6	90.7	205.	1100
M8V	5.0	2.27	5.13	2.63	2.63	2.86	4.19	6.44	10.2	16.6	28.1	51.4	104.	244.	1530
G8III	5.0	1.34	2.88	2.55	2.55	2.64	3.80	5.79	9.11	14.7	24.7	44.5	88.1	198.	1050
K3III	5.0	1.49	3.07	2.56	2.56	2.62	3.78	5.76	9.05	14.6	24.5	44.0	87.0	194.	995.
M0III	5.0	1.67	3.58	2.58	2.58	2.66	3.84	5.86	9.22	14.9	25.0	45.0	89.3	200.	1040
M7III	5.0	3.08	6.56	2.68	2.68	3.02	4.47	6.91	11.0	17.9	30.6	56.7	116.	285.	2010
B0IB	5.0	0.76	1.69	2.48	2.48	2.60	3.74	5.69	8.95	14.5	24.3	43.7	86.7	196.	1100

Appendix A. The GAIA magnitude scale

Signal-to-noise ratios, detection limits and the astrometric precision basically depend on the stellar photon flux folded through the instrument transmittance and QE curves. The corresponding wavelength band is very wide, and does not correlate well with any of the standard photometric passbands such as V , R or I . The effective wavelength varies from nearly that of V for very blue stars to I for very red stars. It is useful to introduce a special magnitude scale G defined by the GAIA (astrometric) passband. Following standard photometric practice, the zero point should be fixed such that $G = V$ for stars of colour index 0 (e.g. $V - I = 0$).

Flux calculations by C. Jordi (using Kurucz models) and myself (using spectrophotometry from [4]), with assumptions as in Sections 2.4 and 2.5, show that a main sequence star with $V = 0$ and $V - I = 0$ generates a flux of $e_0 = 3.42 \times 10^{10} \text{ e s}^{-1}$. For an arbitrary stellar spectrum the GAIA magnitude is given by $G = -2.5 \log(e/e_0)$. The colour index $V - G$ can then be calculated for a range of spectra, including reddened stars.

Using the spectra in [4] it is found that $V - G$ is nearly a unique function of $V - I$ (to within a few hundredths of a magnitude), even for strongly reddened spectra. However, the $V - G/V - I$ relation is strongly non-linear for small $V - I$ and becomes increasingly linear for large $V - I$. This is not the type of relation which is easily represented by a (single) polynomial. The following expression was found to describe the relation quite well in the whole interval from $V - I = -0.35$ to 7:

$$V - G = -0.524 + 0.496 \times \sqrt{1 + (V - I + 0.3)^2} + 0.067 \times (V - I + 0.3)^2. \quad (4)$$

It should be noted that the astrometric precision depends not only on the detected flux but also on the width of the PSF, which varies with colour. The precision is therefore not a unique function of G (cf. Tables 5 and 8).

Appendix B. Calculation of detection probability

The present analysis is based on an ‘aperture photometry’ approach with a fixed threshold in the estimated signal-to-noise ratio R . It is assumed that N_s samples are taken in an area including the star, and N_b samples in a (nearby or surrounding) area including only background. The total counts n_s and n_b in the two areas are modelled as:

$$n_s \sim \text{Poisson}(\alpha + N_s\beta) + \text{N}(0, N_s r^2) \quad (5)$$

$$n_b \sim \text{Poisson}(N_b\beta) + \text{N}(0, N_b r^2) \quad (6)$$

where α is the total star signal (in electrons), β the background (in electrons per sample) and r the RMS read-out noise (in electrons). (Note that β is not exactly the same as in Section 2.7.) The mean values and variances of the counts are $E(n_s) = \alpha + N_s\beta$, $E(n_b) = N_b\beta$, $\text{Var}(n_s) = \alpha + N_s(\beta + r^2)$, and $\text{Var}(n_b) = N_b(\beta + r^2)$. n_s and n_b are statistically independent.

With $q = N_s/N_b$ the star signal is estimated as

$$\hat{\alpha} = n_s - qn_b. \quad (7)$$

We have $\text{Var}(\hat{\alpha}) = \text{Var}(n_s) + q^2 \text{Var}(n_b) = \alpha + (1+q)N_s(\beta + r^2)$. In practice this must also be estimated from the counts, by inserting $\hat{\alpha}$ for α and $\hat{\beta} = n_b/N_b$ for β . (It is assumed that r is known.) This gives

$$\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{\alpha}) = n_s + q^2 n_b + (1+q)N_s r^2. \quad (8)$$

The signal-to-noise ratio may therefore be calculated as:

$$R = \frac{n_s - qn_b}{\sqrt{n_s + q^2 n_b + (1+q)N_s r^2}}. \quad (9)$$

Simulations show that R is approximately normal with unit variance (at least for small R) and mean value

$$R_0 = \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{\alpha + (1+q)N_s(\beta + r^2)}}. \quad (10)$$

Using a threshold $R_{\min}$ therefore gives the detection probability

$$p_{\text{det}}(\alpha) = (2\pi)^{-1/2} \int_{R_{\min} - R_0(\alpha)}^{\infty} \exp(-x^2/2) dx. \quad (11)$$

(In particular, $R_0 = 0$ gives the probability of false detection.)

Empirically I have found that Equation (11) may be approximated (to sufficient accuracy for the present purpose) with the simpler formula

$$p_{\text{det}}(\alpha) = \left[1 + \left(\frac{\alpha_0 R_{\lim}}{\alpha} \right)^{2R_{\lim}} \right]^{-1/2} \quad (12)$$

where α_0 is the flux for which $R_0(\alpha_0) = 1.27$. This formula illustrates nicely how the steepness of the selection function (p_{det} versus magnitude) increases with $R_{\lim}$.

For the PSM it is assumed that samples of 2×2 pixels are read out with an equivalent read-out noise of 15 electrons per sample. Using $N_s = 9$, $N_b = 30$ and $\beta = 3$ electrons per sample gives $\alpha_0 = 66$ electrons. With $R_{\lim} = 3.0$, Equation (12) gives the detection probabilities in Table 2.